

Review

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Guidelines and checklists for writing guidelines and checklists: Lessons from evidence-based medicine

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Abstract

Evidence-based medicine (EBM) is *literature-based medicine*. The essence of EBM is ensuring that research is adequately reported in the literature, not only to help readers determine whether the research is sound but also to ascertain that it can be applied appropriately to specific patients and conditions. This need to document clinical research gave rise to the standards-reporting movement in medicine, the first and best-known standard being the 1996 CONSORT statement for reporting randomized controlled trials. Guidelines and checklists are widely used to augment memory, improve quality and consistency, ensure thoroughness and efficiency, structure repetitive tasks, and to reduce errors, omissions, ambiguities, and misunderstandings. These characteristics make them ideal for reporting the designs, activities, and results of medical research. In fact, EBM is built around developing and using guidelines and checklists. As an early participant in the clinical guideline movement, I learned a lot about how and how not to prepare guidelines. I describe my lessons here.

Keywords:

Checklists, CONSORT, EQUATOR Network, evidence-based medicine, reporting guidelines, research quality

Introduction

Throughout history, physicians have relied on their training and observations when making treatment decisions, an approach called *experience-based medicine* or sometimes *eminence-based medicine* (that is, doing what their mentor did).¹ In the past 50 years, however, physicians began to consider more seriously the findings of modern medical research, especially randomized clinical trials (RCTs) and systematic reviews of these trials, an approach called *evidence-based medicine* (EBM).² The evidence needed to practise EBM is published in the peer-reviewed literature. As a result, EBM is, in fact, *literature-based medicine*. That is, the quality of EBM is directly related to the quality of the literature, which in turn is based on sound research that is accurately and adequately reported. Many medical writers and editors help prepare manuscripts for publication or presentation. That is, they help improve the quality of the medical literature and hence the quality of literature-based medicine and EBM. Knowing how to interpret and apply these guidelines is thus a useful and marketable skill.

The beginnings of the evidence-based medicine movement

One early event in the EBM movement was the creation of the Asilomar Working Group of journal editors, statisticians, clinical researchers, and medical writers. The group met at the Asilomar State Conference Center in Monterey, California, to develop guidelines for reporting randomized trials.³ The meeting was held during the American Medical Writers Association's annual Asilomar regional conference. I attended the conference and, because of my work in reporting statistics, was invited to join the meeting. It was the beginning of a 35-year participation in the guidelines movement.

About the time the Asilomar group was meeting, another group was developing a similar set of guidelines in the UK: the Standards of Reporting Trials (SORT) Group, which comprised leading experts in EBM.⁴ Drummond Rennie, MD, for many years an associate editor at *JAMA*, was a member of both groups and suggested that they combine their efforts. The result was the 1993 CONSolidated Standards Of Reporting Trials Group, now known as the CONSORT Group.⁵ This same group would eventually establish the EQUATOR network (Enhancing the QUality and Transparency Of health Research), which is a clearing house for hundreds of EBM guidelines. The website also contains articles on how to develop guidelines, lists of guidelines under development, and advertisements for training opportunities.⁶

Over the years, I participated in several groups, developing guidelines as well as writing some myself. This article describes the lessons I learned about how to write reporting guidelines; lessons that generalize to preparing reporting guidelines and checklists for any purpose. Over the years, participation in several groups involved in developing and writing guidelines has contributed to the insights presented in this article. The article describes lessons learned about how to write reporting guidelines – lessons that may be generalized to the preparation of reporting guidelines and checklists for any purpose.

Guidelines vs checklists

Guidelines and checklists often refer to the same concept: a list of questions or statements, each of which requires a response of some kind that guides users in providing information to assist in decision-making. Guidelines tend to be broader and more general than checklists, which tend to be more specific and task-oriented. Most EBM statements include both guidelines and checklists.

For example, in the CONSORT statement for reporting harms,⁷ Item 14 is a checklist item that asks for specific information: “[Report] dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up.” The dates are either given or not. In comparison, Item 2 is more of a guideline: “[Describe the] Scientific background and explanation of rationale [of the study].” Readers must determine whether the description and explanation are adequate to meet a given purpose. The more specific the better, but some items of necessity must be broader.

Descriptive vs prescriptive guidelines

When developing a guideline, the most fundamental decision is determining whether it should be descriptive, prescriptive, or both. Descriptive guidelines focus on documenting *what has happened* and sometimes on what might happen (“If this, then that” statements). Most of the guidelines listed on the EQUATOR website are descriptive.

In contrast, prescriptive guidelines are directive and perhaps even instructional; they tell *what should be done*. An example is the SAGER Guidelines (Sex And Gender Equity in Research), which focus on improving sex- and gender-reporting in research.⁸ Although “primarily designed to guide authors in preparing their manuscripts,” the guidelines depend on researchers prospectively collecting and analyzing specific information. Traditional categories pose few problems. Data on sex are routinely collected in research, although often not analyzed or reported by sex. New definitions of sex and gender, however, may require that data on these new categories be prospectively collected and analyzed. Hence, these guidelines are partly prescriptive because they cannot be met after the research is completed.

Evidence-based medicine guidelines are almost always descriptive. Other than that difference in purpose, however, the general

advice on developing guidelines and checklists is the same.

The development of guidelines for evidence-based medicine

The 1996 CONSORT Guidelines⁵ were the first of literally hundreds of guidelines developed for reporting clinical research designs and activities (Table 1). Most of these guidelines have the same form as the CONSORT guidelines: an annotated checklist for reporting research designs, conduct, and outcomes; often a flowchart showing the number of patients who remain in the study at key time points, and sometimes an “explanation and elaboration” (E&E) paper that explains each guideline in detail and gives examples.

Many of the guidelines have been developed similarly. A small group sees a need for a new guideline. The members might then conduct a comprehensive literature review on the topic, hold an organizing meeting at a professional conference, or perhaps use an international web-based Delphi process to survey experts in the field to generate ideas

Table 1. Common reporting guidelines available on the EQUATOR website

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1. **CONSORT** Consolidated Standards of Reporting [randomized] Trials
 2. **PRISMA** Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
 3. **STROBE** Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology
 4. **CARE** Guidelines for Reporting Case Reports
 5. **STARD** Standards for Reporting of Diagnostic Accuracy
 6. **SPRIT** Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials
 7. **AGREE** Appraisal of Guidelines REsearch and Evaluation
 8. **CHEERS** Consolidated Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards
 9. **ARRIVE** Animal Research: Reporting of In Vivo Experiments
 10. **CLIP** Principles for reporting Clinical and Laboratory Images in Publications
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or to achieve consensus. They might convene an international meeting of experts who draft a set of guidelines or perhaps approve a final draft of the guidelines. Sometimes, all of these procedures are used.

In my experience, the discussions at these meetings are not so much about what information to ask for as about identifying the most important information, determining the specific wording of each guideline, and then adjusting the number of guidelines or the length of the checklist to create a manageable document.

When the group has a guideline in final form, it is usually submitted for publication to one or more journals, often for simultaneous publication. In this case, all the journals and the authors have to agree on the final form and production schedule before publication. The first CONSORT guidelines⁵ were published simultaneously in six journals; the OHstat

Guidelines for reporting oral health research were published simultaneously in five.⁹

Lessons learned in developing guidelines for evidence-based medicine

“The primary role of reporting guidelines is to remind researchers what information to include in the manuscript, not to tell them how to do research.”

Doug Altman and Iveta Simera, two founders of the EQUATOR Network.⁶

Evidence-based medicine guidelines should always be descriptive

Reporting guidelines should ask authors to document their research, not to tell them what they should have done (Table 2). The primary goal of EBM guidelines is to get

Table 2. Prescriptive methodological guidelines vs descriptive reporting guidelines. Prescriptive guidelines are considered inappropriate for preparing publications because they tell authors what they should have done, after the fact. An appropriate descriptive guideline tells authors to report what they did, right or wrong

Prescriptive methodological guidelines	Descriptive reporting guidelines
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document the reason(s) for conducting the study. State all the hypotheses, keeping the study objectives in mind. • Explain why the trial design is appropriate. • Define the inclusion and exclusion criteria used in sample selection and why these criteria were chosen. • Justify the sample size for the stated precision, alpha error, and/or statistical power. • Report normally distributed data with means and standard deviations and skewed distributions with medians and interquartile ranges or tell how the distribution was transformed for analysis. • Before comparing two or more groups with respect to outcomes in terms of summaries such as means, proportions in different categories, and rates, confirm that the groups are comparable with regard to the baseline composition of the subjects for factors (such as the age distribution) that can affect the outcome. • Confirm that the data conformed to the assumptions of the statistical tests used to analyse them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tell why the study was done. • Identify the trial design. • Describe the patients studied and tell why they were included or excluded from the study. • Tell how the sample size was determined. • Provide descriptive statistics for each outcome variable studied, by experimental group. • Identify the comparisons made in the study. • Identify the statistical tests or procedures used to analyse the data.

authors to provide enough detail so that reviewers and readers can adequately evaluate the research. Authors generally consult publication guidelines only shortly before the final manuscript is submitted for publication, well past the time when directives for conducting research or analysis would do any good. Nevertheless, this desire to include prescriptive methodological guidelines was evident in several of the meetings I attended. For example, one group wanted to publish an 8-page list of “guidelines,” which turned out to be an unorganized list of pet peeves with the admonition to “do things our way.” Later, I realized that this situation could be addressed by including a “best practices” section in the “Explanation and Elaboration” paper.

Ideally, guidelines and checklists will be unidimensional, not multidimensional

Guideline groups understandably want to keep the number of guidelines to a minimum. The more complex the guidelines, the less likely they will be used. The 1996 CONSORT Statement had 21 guidelines,⁵ and the 2001 update had 22,¹⁰ although it was really not so much an expansion of the former as it was a more refined version. With each meeting, however, it became clear that the group wanted more details about the research but not more guidelines. The solution was to make some guidelines multidimensional.

This result was apparent in the 2010 CONSORT update, which has 25 numbered guidelines – but asks 53 questions¹¹ – as well as in the recently released 2025 update, which has 30 numbered guidelines asking 41 questions.¹²

For example, in CONSORT 2025,¹² Guideline 24a has four parts.

1. Describe the “intervention and comparator as they were actually administered, and if appropriate”
2. “Who delivered the intervention/comparator”

3. “How participants adhered”
4. “Whether they [intervention and comparator] were delivered as intended (fidelity)”

These items are reasonable and appropriately grouped in the same guideline, but authors need to consider four requests, not one, and Guideline 24b (“Concomitant care received during the trial for each group”) is a fifth request – in other words, Guideline 24 is multidimensional.

Reporting guidelines are for documenting research, not evaluating it

Reporting guidelines can assess *the adequacy of the documentation* of research, but they should not be used to evaluate *the quality of research* itself, although it is commonly done.¹³⁻¹⁹ The usual approach is to check off each guideline considered to be met in the article. The number or percentage of met guidelines becomes the quality score. This approach has some obvious shortcomings.

1. Of necessity, reporting guidelines identify only the *minimum* amount of information about a trial.¹³
2. Not all guidelines are equally relevant to study quality: Guideline 1: “Identify the study as a randomized trial” vs Guideline 14: “Prespecified primary and secondary outcomes, including the specific measurement variable (for example, systolic blood pressure), analysis metric (for example, change from baseline, final value, time to event), method of aggregation (for example, median, proportion), and time point for each outcome.”
3. Not every dimension of a multidimensional guideline may have been addressed.
4. Similarities in the quality of reporting may hide important differences in methodological quality, and

well-conducted trials may be reported badly. “A clear distinction should be made between these 2 dimensions [reporting quality and methodological quality] of the quality of RCTs.”¹³

Guidelines can include prompts as well as requirements

By design, the CONSORT-related guidelines identify the minimum information required to evaluate a trial. However, in the development meetings, it was universally understood that other information is almost always needed. Further, this additional information would likely vary widely from trial to trial and so could not be addressed with specific guidelines. As above, multidimensional guidelines might include some of this additional information, but they are not ideal. An alternative (although one not yet widely implemented) is to speak not of guidelines or requirements but of prompts.

How to Report Statistics in Medicine, a comprehensive set of statistical and methodological reporting guidelines, provides 73 prompts for reporting RCTs.²⁰ Essentially, authors are presented with suggestions that might improve their manuscript, not guidelines that need to be addressed. Of course, the 73 prompts include the CONSORT and other guidelines, but they also include other, more detailed, points authors might (or might not) want to consider.

Guideline 13.31: Describe any quality control methods used to ensure the completeness and accuracy of data collection and management.

Guideline 13.40: Indicate how observations based on judgements were assessed for consistency or agreement.

Guideline 13.66: Report any anecdotal evidence or observations that may contribute to a more accurate or complete understanding of the trial or its results.

Guidelines can include or refer to other guidelines

The OHStat Guidelines (Reporting Observational Studies and Clinical Trials in Oral Health Research⁹) draw from the CONSORT¹⁰ and STROBE guidelines for experimental and observational studies, respectively,²¹ and the E&E paper includes the SAMPL guidelines for reporting statistics,²² the CONSORT Harms guidelines,⁷ the CLIP principles for documenting images,²³ and the GRADE guidelines for summarizing research results.²⁴ It is difficult enough to get authors to follow one guideline, much less two or more. OHStat has 48 guidelines, including key prompts from other guidelines.⁹ The result is that authors need to consult only one guideline, not six. This convenience should increase the likelihood that the OHStat Guidelines will be used, although the most important factor in using guidelines is whether journals are willing to require their use, as opposed to just endorsing or referring to them. About three-quarters (245 of 337) of high-impact medical journals endorse – but do not require – the use of guidelines,²⁵ but currently, overall endorsement by journals is inconsistent, with only a small number endorsing guidelines.^{26–29}

Guidelines can include recommendations for preparing manuscripts in addition to reporting research

Reminding authors that the characteristics of their manuscripts can be as important as those of their research should, in theory, improve the quality of the published article.

For example, below are some excerpts from the OHStat Guidelines⁹:

1. **Title:** “Character limits notwithstanding, try to include in the title as many of the SPICED-T elements as possible: Setting, Patients, Intervention, Comparator, Endpoint, Design,

and sometimes Time frame.” (This SPICED-T mnemonic can help authors write better titles faster and to shorten them more easily to meet character limits by removing the least important elements first.^{9,30})

2. **Consistency:** “Confirm that all information in the abstract is identical to that in the article, especially the conclusions.”^{9,30}

Abstracts are usually the first and often the only part of an article read. In a high proportion of abstracts – far more than half in most studies – important information is missing from or inconsistent with that in the accompanying article.³¹ A simple reminder to authors, editors, and reviewers to make sure that the abstract is consistent with the text should help reduce this potentially serious error.

The OHStat Guidelines also recommend a structured discussion:^{9,30}

42. Summary: Summarize the study and the main results.

43. Interpretation: Interpret the results cautiously and suggest an explanation for them.

44. Integration: Compare the results with what else is known about the problem (review the literature).

45. Generalization: Discuss the generalizability of the results (their external validity).

46. Implications: If reasonable, comment on the applications or implications of the results on health care delivery.

47. Limitations: Describe likely sources, directions, and magnitudes of errors and bias if they were not controlled for in the study design.

48. Conclusions: List the conclusions in terms of a clinically important outcome measure. Do not restate the results; give their implications.

Although not included in the OHStat E&E guidelines, authors can be encouraged to write a good four-part introduction:³⁰

Part 1: A *background statement* that provides the context for understanding the problem and the approach to addressing it.

Part 2: A *problem statement* that describes the nature, scope, severity or importance of the problem, or the gap in knowledge that stimulated the research.

Part 3: An *activity statement* that details the research question, hypothesis, approach, or activities undertaken to investigate the problem

Part 4: A *forecasting statement* that tells readers what they will find if they continue to read the article.

Consider writing an “Explanation and Elaboration” paper for the guidelines

Since the beginning, the CONSORT guidelines have been accompanied by an E&E paper that explains each guideline in detail, tells why it is important, gives examples of good and poor reporting, and provides references for all of this information.⁵ (If I were to teach a class on RCTs, I would use the CONSORT E&E paper as the main text.) In addition to the paper’s educational value, however, the guidelines are more easily implemented if authors understand why the information is important.

The audience(s) and purpose(s) of the guidelines should determine its content, organization, and presentation

I once came across a “good bad example set” of statistical reporting guidelines.³³ They were proposed by a statistician and appear to be directed more to other statisticians than to authors. For example, almost all the guidelines required a statistical background strong enough to know which specific statistical procedures each guideline applied. Limited

specific reporting guidelines are given only for three analyses: regression (253 words), survival analysis (101 words), and correlation (89 words). In contrast, each of these topics is a complete chapter in *How to Report Statistics in Medicine*.²⁰ The guideline for reporting “correlation and cause and effect,” which is prescriptive in more than one instance, reads as follows.

“14a. Report the value of the relevant correlation coefficient. If described as low, moderate or high, give the categories with their biological implications. Interpret conventional Pearson correlation coefficient for assessing linear relationship and not for any general relationship between continuous variables. For association between categorical variables, include the full contingency table and explain if any categories were merged for analysis purpose. 14b Distinguish between association/correlation and cause-effect. If cause-effect is implied, rule out all possible alternative explanations such as the role of confounders and biases. 14c. Distinguish correlation/association from agreement.”

Do not require stylistic or self-evident information

Stylistic or self-evident information does not interfere with understanding; it is just unnecessary. For example, common and accepted terms need not be defined. The requirement to report distributions as “mean (SD)” and not “mean \pm SD” is unnecessary because they mean the same. (By definition, the standard deviation applies to both sides of the mean, so the “ \pm ” is irrelevant.) Likewise, the requirement to report *P* values to one decimal place if *n* < 100 and to two decimal places for *n* \geq 100 is common practice. The underlying guideline is to report data with the appropriate degree of precision, which is a widely accepted norm in research.

Asking authors to do their own copyediting is not always useful because (1) they often will not do it and (2) journals want full control over the published article so they will usually fix self-evident and stylistic errors themselves.

Use language readers will understand

Understandably, most authors are concerned primarily (if not exclusively) with content. The problem is that content, to be effective, has to be tailored to a specific audience, with a specific purpose, through an appropriate medium. A guideline written with a poor sense of audience can frustrate authors who are already disinclined to use guidelines:

“If dichotomous or polytomous categories have been used in analysis of continuous variables, explain the rationale of these categories in terms of clinical implication.”³³

In plain English:

“If a variable measured on a continuous scale of measurement is divided into two or more categories, such as large, medium, and small, explain why the categories were created, how they were defined (give the values of cut-points defining each category), and the possible clinical implications of reducing the precision of measurement.”

Use informative titles, not descriptive ones

Descriptive titles are labels for abstract concepts, for example, “variables”: the title does not indicate whether the text will define a variable, how variables were chosen, how they were measured, how they were selected for multivariate analyses, how they were to be reported, or all of the above. In contrast, informative titles connect the needs of readers with the content they need: “Identify and summarize the variables used in the analysis” (Table 3).³⁰

Table 3. Descriptive and informative headings (or titles) Descriptive headings are labels for abstract concepts, whereas informative headings provide readers with the information they need to quickly find what they are looking for. The headings in the descriptive column are numbered, although that supposes that the headings have a given order, which they do not. The headings in the informative column are not numbered because they do not need to be

Descriptive headings for reporting statistics	Informative headings for reporting statistics
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hypothesis 2. Variables under study 3. Antecedents and outcomes 4. Descriptive summaries 5. Modification of raw data 6. Baseline information 7. Comparability of two or more groups 8. Main method of analysis estimation 9. Tests of statistical hypothesis 10. Robustness of results 11. Correlation and cause-effect 12. Regression analysis 13. Survival analysis 	<p>General principles for reporting statistical results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reporting numbers and descriptive statistics Reporting risk, rates, and ratios Reporting hypothesis tests Reporting association analyses Reporting correlation analyses Reporting regression analyses Reporting analysis of variance (ANOVA) or of covariance (ANCOVA) Reporting survival (time-to-event) analysis Reporting Bayesian analyses

Be careful about numbering guidelines

Numbering is useful when the elements in a list have a sequence, when every element must be addressed (that is, it is a checklist), when the information is generally ordered (in that guidelines with higher numbers generally appear later in the manuscript), and when it is easier to refer to a guideline’s number than to its name.

Not all topics involve a sequence. Individual statistical procedures are “nominal categories” with no inherent order. Numbering them makes them appear to be “ordinal” or “ranked” categories, which they are not. The examples of informative headings in Table 3 are not numbered because they do not need to be: numbering them would imply a relationship among them that is not true.

Avoid unnecessary duplication but consider using “selective redundancy” of text

“Selective redundancy” refers to the strategy of including an identical guideline in two or more stand-alone sets of guidelines so that authors can find everything they need in one set without having to remember that there is a single guideline that applies to more than one set of guidelines (Table 4).

This approach may be seen as “unnecessary duplication” of some guidelines. However, readers want to know how to report the

results of a specific statistical method, so it makes sense to organize the guidelines into separate, self-contained modules that list all the guidelines relevant to each method. Thus, “unnecessary duplication” is really selective redundancy and means that guidelines should be organized around how readers will use

Table 4. “Selective redundancy” Selective redundancy uses duplication (here, indicated by larger font and italics) to create a single comprehensive source for, in this case, statistical procedures. The redundancy allows authors to find all the guidelines they need in one place

<p>Reporting association analyses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Describe the relationship of interest.</i> • <i>Summarize the variables used with descriptive statistics.</i> • Identify the test of association used <p>Reporting regression analyses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Describe the relationship of interest.</i> • <i>Summarize the variables used with descriptive statistics.</i> • For linear regressions, report the model [the equation]. <p>Reporting analysis of variance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>State the hypothesis being tested.</i> • <i>Identify the explanatory and response variables.</i> • Tell whether the variables were tested for interaction. <p>Reporting survival (time-to-event) analyses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>State the hypothesis being tested.</i> • <i>Identify the explanatory and response variables.</i> • Specify the circumstances under which data were censored.

Table 5. General guidelines for reporting statistical analyses. The single paragraph (left-hand column) is visually dense, hard to read, and difficult to use in determining whether the guideline(s) have been met. In contrast, text in the form of a list of bullet points, although longer, is easier to navigate

A narrative description ³³	List of bullet points ²²
<p>12a. State the statistical hypothesis for each test. Give the name of each test and its exact P value with (degrees of freedom) where relevant. For $P < 0.001$, state with the “less than” sign and for $P > 0.999$, with the “more than” sign. Indicate whether the test is one-tailed or two-tailed and the reasons thereof. Avoid the use of the term “statistical significance” and do not mention significance level (such as $\alpha = 0.05$) for your results. Mention any adjustment made for multiple comparisons and for using multiple tests for any conclusion. Distinguish between family-wise error rate and experiment-wise error rate. Also mention the confidence intervals for the effect size such as mean difference between the groups.</p>	<p>Primary analyses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State the purpose of the analysis. • Identify the variables used. • Verify the method(s) of data analysis and summarize each with descriptive statistics. • When possible, identify the smallest difference considered to be clinically important. • Describe fully the main methods for analysing the primary objectives of the study. • Make clear which method was used for each analysis. • Confirm that the assumptions of each test were met. • Indicate whether and how any allowance or adjustments were made for performing multiple hypothesis tests on the same data. • If relevant, report how any outlying data were treated in the analysis. • Say whether tests were one- or two-tailed and justify the use of one-tailed tests. • Report the alpha level (for example, 0.05) that defines statistical significance. • Name the statistical program used in the analysis.

them, not just that the guidelines are included somewhere in the document.

A similar example is the STROBE guidelines for reporting observational studies: case-control, cross-sectional, and cohort studies.¹⁶ These designs appear as subheadings in several individual guidelines because each has different documentation needs.

Consider presenting guidelines as itemized bullet points rather than as narrative descriptions

One of my favourite definitions of intelligence is “knowing what to attend to.”³⁰

Bulleted lists help readers *attend* to one guideline at a time. In narrative descriptions that include two or more related guidelines in a paragraph, the need for punctuation and complete sentences can make finding a specific guideline harder (Table 5). Checklists are usually bulleted for this reason.

A final thought

Medical writers and editors are the link between people who create new information and those who use that information. It is

well worth the time and effort to learn how to accurately characterize audiences, determine the purpose(s) of a communication, and present information effectively to make guidelines as easy as possible to find, understand, remember, and use. Further, writers and editors who help prepare manuscripts for publication are essentially improving the quality of the scientific literature. Because EBM is literature-based medicine, a thorough knowledge of EBM reporting guidelines can substantially increase our value added to employers and clients by ensuring that biomedical research is reported adequately and accurately.

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